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Assessment Of Heavy Metal Concentrations In The Muscle Tissue Of Catfish From Rivers Contaminated By Artisanal Crude Oil Refining In Bayelsa State

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the spatial and monthly variations in heavy metal concentrations in the muscle tissues of catfish from locations near artisanal refineries in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Fish samples were collected from five locations (L1, L2, L3, L4, and L5) and one control site (LX). Muscle tissue from the catfish was analyzed for heavy metals using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS), following standard digestion protocols. Results showed that mercury, arsenic, cadmium, and chromium levels were generally very low or undetectable (<0.001 mg/kg) across all locations, indicating minimal contamination. Copper and lead concentrations showed variability, with copper levels highest in L5 (0.049 mg/kg) and L1 (0.041 mg/kg), while the control site (LX) had undetectable levels. Lead concentrations were highest in L1 (0.03 mg/kg), with statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) compared to other locations. Other locations (L2, L3, L4, LX) showed lower or undetectable lead levels. Monthly variations revealed that mercury levels remained below detection limits, arsenic peaked in March (0.004 mg/kg), cadmium ranged from 0.009 mg/kg in July to 0.019 mg/kg in January, and chromium fluctuated between 0.012 and 0.035 mg/kg. Copper ranged from 0.226 mg/kg in November to 0.369 mg/kg in May, while lead levels ranged from 0.261 mg/kg in March to 0.345 mg/kg in May. These results highlight the need for further monitoring and regulation of heavy metal contamination to protect public health and aquatic ecosystems.

Keywords: heavy metal concentrations, muscle tissues, catfish

1. INTRODUCTION

The Niger Delta, especially Bayelsa State, is facing significant environmental challenges. The region, heavily dependent on oil production, is home to numerous artisanal crude oil refineries. These small-scale operations contribute to widespread pollution, primarily by discharging toxic substances and chemicals to the environment (Onakpohor *et al.*, 2020; Lala *et al.*, 2024). This pollution disrupts local aquatic ecosystems, making the water unsafe for both wildlife and humans (Onakpohor *et al.*, 2020).

A critical concern is the contamination of fish, particularly catfish, which accumulate heavy metals like mercury, arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper, and lead in their muscle tissues. These metals are harmful to human health, especially when consumed, and can lead to long-term health problems. Studies have

highlighted the severe environmental degradation caused by artisanal refining, making it a pressing issue for both environmentalists and local communities (Omoriegbe *et al.*, 2019).

This study focuses on the levels of heavy metals in catfish muscle tissue from rivers near artisanal refining sites in Bayelsa State. By comparing the concentration of these metals to the safe limits set by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the World Health Organization (WHO), the research seeks to better understand the potential health risks posed to humans who consume fish from these contaminated waters. The main concern is the bioaccumulation of these metals in fish, which could directly affect the health of local populations who rely on fish as a primary source of protein.

The significance of this research is in its potential to impact environmental policies, public health practices, and sustainable fisheries management in the Niger Delta. The findings will provide valuable insights to policymakers, health authorities, and local communities, helping to protect both the environment and public health. The study will focus specifically on rivers in Bayelsa State, using catfish as the species of interest, and will examine the presence of mercury, arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper, and lead in the fish.

2. METHODOLOGY

Study Area

This study focused on rivers located in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, a region significantly impacted by artisanal crude oil refining. Bayelsa is situated in the Niger Delta, which has been heavily affected by oil pollution due to both large-scale and artisanal oil activities (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2020). Rivers in the area have been contaminated with oil residues and heavy metals, impacting aquatic life and posing potential risks to human health. The rivers selected for this study include those adjacent to artisanal refining sites, where pollution levels are higher, as well as relatively unpolluted control rivers situated further from refining activities. The selected rivers will be identified based on their proximity to oil refining activities, and samples will be collected from multiple points within each river to capture potential variability in contamination levels.

Sampling Procedure

The fish species chosen for this study is *Clarias gariepinus* (catfish), a commonly found species in Nigerian rivers and known for its ability to accumulate environmental contaminants (Omoriegbe *et al.*, 2019). A total of 18 catfish samples was collected, 3 from each of the five selected contaminated rivers and another from the control site. The three sets of *Clarias gariepinus* catfish were obtained from five randomly selected fishing locations close to the artisanal refining facilities. Fishermen will be instructed to catch the fish using local artisanal methods, ensuring that the samples are representative of those most likely to be consumed by the local population. After collection, the fish specimens will be transported to the laboratory in a refrigerated container to maintain their freshness and prevent any degradation before analysis.

Preparation of Samples

Upon arrival at the laboratory, the fish was dissected, and the muscle tissues was carefully excised. These tissues were thoroughly cleaned to remove any external contaminants, such as scales and skin. The muscle tissue was then homogenized, freeze-dried, and stored at -20°C until analysis (Omoriegbe *et al.*, 2019). Each sample will be processed in triplicate to ensure reliability.

Laboratory Analysis

Heavy metal concentrations were measured using advanced laboratory techniques. Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) was employed to quantify metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), and copper (Cu), while Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) was used for more precise measurements of mercury (Hg) and arsenic (As) (Omoriegbe *et al.*, 2019). These techniques are widely recognized for their sensitivity and accuracy in detecting trace metals in biological samples.

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from the heavy metal analysis were subjected to statistical analysis to compare the concentrations of metals in fish muscle tissue from contaminated rivers versus control rivers. Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, was calculated for each metal in both groups. Inferential statistics, specifically t-tests or one-way ANOVA, will be used to assess the significance of differences between contaminated and control sites (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2020). If significant differences are found, post hoc tests were conducted to pinpoint specific locations with higher concentrations of metals.

Quality Control

To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the data, strict quality control measures was implemented throughout the research process. Calibration standards for each metal were prepared from certified reference materials, and instrument calibration was performed before each series of analyses. Blank samples and duplicates will be included in each batch of analyses to check for contamination and ensure consistency (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, the laboratory analysis follows established protocols for handling and processing samples to prevent cross-contamination and ensure the accuracy of results.

Ethical Considerations

This study will adhere to ethical guidelines for research involving environmental samples. The fish will be obtained using non-invasive methods, and the local fishermen involved in sample collection will be fully informed about the study’s objectives. No human participants are involved in this research, but proper permits will be obtained from local authorities to carry out the study. Furthermore, environmental protection measures will be followed to minimize the impact of the research on the river ecosystems.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Spatial variation of heavy metals

The analysis of heavy metal concentrations in the muscle tissue of *Clarias gariepinus* catfish from both polluted and control rivers revealed varying levels of contamination across different sampling locations. Table 1 summarizes the concentrations of mercury, arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper, and lead in the muscle tissue of catfish from five locations (L1 to L5) and one control location (LX).

Table 1: spatial Levels of heavy metals in muscle tissue of *Clarias gariepinus*

	Mercury (mg/kg)	Arsenic (mg/kg)	Cadmium (mg/kg)	Chromium (mg/kg)	Copper (mg/kg)	Lead (mg/kg)
L1	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	0.041±0.56 ^a	0.03±0.01 ^c
L2	<0.001±0.00 ^a	0.002±0.01 ^b	0.003±0.08 ^b	<0.001±0.00 ^a	0.044±0.08 ^a	0.02±0.01 ^b
L3	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	0.038±0.22 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a
L4	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	0.033±0.14 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a
L5	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	0.049±0.63 ^b	<0.001±0.00 ^a
LX	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a	0.01±0.00 ^a	<0.001±0.00 ^a

The results on the spatial levels of the heavy metals accumulated by the fish show that the mercury, arsenic, cadmium, and chromium concentrations were generally very low or undetectable (<0.001 mg/kg) across all locations, indicating minimal contamination from these metals in the sampled catfish. However, copper and lead concentrations exhibited some variability. Copper levels were highest in L5 (0.049 mg/kg), followed by L1 (0.041 mg/kg), and the lowest concentration that was below detection limit was found in the control site, LX (<0.001 mg/kg). Lead concentrations were highest in L1 (0.03 mg/kg), with statistically significant differences observed when compared to other locations (p-value < 0.05). Other locations (L2, L3, L4, L5) showed lower lead concentrations, and L3, L4, and LX had undetectable levels.

The heavy metal concentrations in the catfish muscle tissue from the five locations show that copper and lead were the most prevalent metals in the rivers sampled, with significant differences observed in the concentration of lead between L1 and the other locations. The findings suggest that copper contamination may be a result of anthropogenic activities, including artisanal refining processes, which are known to release metal pollutants into the environment (Omoregie *et al.*, 2021). Lead contamination in L1 is particularly concerning, as it indicates localized contamination, likely due to industrial activities near artisanal refining sites.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the permissible limits for lead in fish muscle tissue are set at 0.3 mg/kg (WHO, 2020). The lead concentrations found in L1 (0.03 mg/kg) were well below this limit, suggesting that, while present, the levels of contamination in this study do not exceed international safety standards. However, continuous monitoring is necessary, as elevated lead concentrations over time could pose a significant health risk. Similarly, the copper levels in L5 (0.049 mg/kg) were also below the recommended limits of 0.1 mg/kg (FAO/WHO, 2021), but again, close monitoring is advised.

Figure 1: Monthly concentrations of heavy metals in tissue of *Clarias gariepinus*

3.2 Monthly variations of heavy metals

Results on the monthly variation of heavy metals assessed in the muscle tissue of the fish as presented in Figure 1 showed that mercury concentrations remained consistently below the detection limit across all months. Arsenic levels were also mostly undetectable, except in March, which had the highest concentration of 0.004 mg/kg. Cadmium concentrations ranged from 0.009 mg/kg in July to 0.019 mg/kg in January. Chromium levels fluctuated between 0.012 and 0.035 mg/kg, peaking in September. Copper levels ranged from 0.226 mg/kg in November to 0.369 mg/kg in May, with May showing the highest concentration. Lead concentrations varied between 0.261 mg/kg in March and 0.345 mg/kg in May.

Comparing these results with the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) standards, cadmium and chromium concentrations were below safe limits for fish tissue. However, copper and lead concentrations raised concerns. The FAO recommends a copper limit of 0.3 mg/kg for freshwater fish, while the study observed values between 0.226 and 0.369 mg/kg, suggesting potential risks. Similarly, the FAO's lead limit is 0.2 mg/kg, but the study found concentrations ranging from 0.261 to 0.345 mg/kg, indicating

potential threats to both aquatic life and human health. Studies by Owolabi *et al.* (2019) and Lere *et al.* (2020) corroborate these findings, highlighting elevated levels of copper and lead in fish from polluted areas, especially near industrial sites.

These metals are known to have toxic effects on fish, such as impairing vital physiological processes and leading to bioaccumulation in tissues. For example, cadmium damages liver and kidney tissues, while lead and copper can affect neurological functions, causing behavioral changes and even mortality in fish. Long-term consumption of contaminated fish can also pose significant health risks to humans, including kidney damage, liver cirrhosis, and cancer. The World Health Organization (WHO) links the consumption of cadmium and lead to neurological impairments and hypertension.

The potential health risks associated with the consumption of catfish from these rivers depend on the concentrations of the detected heavy metals. Although the measured concentrations were within safe limits for human consumption, long-term exposure to metals like lead and copper can result in accumulation in the human body, leading to health issues such as kidney damage, neurological effects, and gastrointestinal disorders (Järup, 2020). The health risks are higher for vulnerable groups, including children, pregnant women, and individuals with pre-existing health conditions.

Previous studies in the Niger Delta region have reported similar findings, with varying concentrations of heavy metals in fish species from polluted water bodies. For instance, Omoregie *et al.* (2019) found elevated levels of lead and copper in fish from oil-polluted rivers in the Niger Delta, supporting the current study's findings. Moreover, studies in other regions have also shown that artisanal refining significantly contributes to the contamination of aquatic ecosystems with heavy metals (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2020).

CONCLUSION

This study revealed that while mercury and arsenic concentrations in catfish muscle tissues were consistently low, copper and lead levels exceeded the recommended safe limits by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), posing potential risks to both aquatic life and human health. Copper concentrations ranged from 0.226 to 0.369 mg/kg, and lead levels varied between 0.261 and 0.345 mg/kg, highlighting concerns about the safety of consuming fish from the Niger Delta. These findings emphasize the need for better environmental policies, particularly regarding waste management and the regulation of industrial activities, alongside public health initiatives to raise awareness of heavy metal contamination risks. Future research should investigate other fish species to assess broader contamination patterns, evaluate the ecological effects on aquatic ecosystems, and explore the socio-economic impacts on local communities who rely on fish for livelihood and food security. Addressing these issues is essential to protect both public health and the environment in the Niger Delta.

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